

Navigating Backlash: Iran's 'Woman, Life, Freedom' Protests and its Aftermath

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Feminist scholars and advocates have long asserted that women's rights and gender equality are fundamental prerequisites for democratic governance. The close correlation between women's rights and democracy is becoming increasingly evident, as the erosion of women's rights often signals early and unmistakable signs of democratic backsliding and the rise of authoritarianism worldwide (Allam 2019; Arat 2022; Chenoweth and Marks 2022). A gendered analysis of state institutions, policymaking, and elections provides crucial insights into the historical fluctuations in women's rights and, by extension, the overall quality of democracy (Tajali 2022). An overview of sexist repression in Iran highlights the depth of autocratic entrenchment, as evidenced by increasing gender-based repression and violence. These assaults on women's fundamental rights are not new but are deeply entrenched in the ideologies of Islamic fundamentalism, which have institutionalized patriarchal dominance and systemic gender discrimination (Hoodfar and Sadr 2010; Paidar 1995; Tajali 2024b). This analysis also exposes the contentious relationship between authoritarian elites and feminist advocates, who refuse to remain passive in the face of such attacks.

Feminist movements that resist systemic gen-

der discrimination pose a significant threat to the Iranian regime, resulting in violent crackdowns on women's rights advocates. A recent example is the regime's harsh response to the non-violent "Woman, Life, Freedom" protests triggered by the killing of 22-year-old Kurdish-Iranian Mahsa Jina Amini in September 2022, while in police custody for allegedly violating Iran's conservative hijab laws. To reassert control, the conservative-dominated Iranian parliament passed a controversial Hijab and Chastity bill in September 2023. This bill introduces harsher penalties for improper veiling, utilizing enhanced surveillance and artificial intelligence to identify those who defy the mandatory hijab laws. While the bill awaits approval from the unelected Guardian Council, Iranian authorities initiated the "Noor (Light) Operation" in April 2024, enforcing the bill's provisions with violent crackdowns on improperly veiled women and girls.

The heightened policing of women's bodies in recent years have been accompanied by a severe crackdown on feminist and women's rights activism nationwide, with particular focus on ethnic minority women advocates. In a troubling trend, women protestors and political prisoners are being sentenced to death amid a rise in political executions since the 2022 protests (Sharifi and Alavi 2024).

Meanwhile, for months, the Iranian regime failed to acknowledge or identify the perpetrators behind the mass poisonings of several all-female high schools and college dormitories across the country from late 2022 until early 2023. Initially, key state authorities dismissed the students' symptoms as mere hysteria and stress. While the Taliban-like attacks were unprecedented for Iran, their targeting of female-only schools highlighted the gendered intent of the attacks, likely aiming to retaliate against young women and girls who were at the frontline of the "Woman, Life, Freedom" protests.

Although it intensified after the 2022 protests, Iran's patriarchal backlash has been solidified through overwhelming conservative control over key state institutions in recent years. This control has had profound gendered repercussions, in line with more regional and global gender backlash. A notable example has been the complete turnaround from Iran's once applauded policies on family planning and contraception during the late 1980s and 1990s (Hoodfar 1996), with the 2021 passage of the Youthful Population and Protection of the Family law. Similar to other pronatalist turns witnessed across the region and the globe, this law greatly restricts women's access to abortion and contraception as well as other previous state funded services in support of sexual and reproductive health, with the aim to address Iran's low fertility rates. The laws' restrictions carry special risks for more disadvantaged and rural social groups who previously relied heavily on state support (Asadisarvestani and Sobotka 2023).

Women and feminist advocates of Iran have not been silent against systemic attacks on women's rights and gender equality. Today, they not only represent a formidable

pro-democratic force in the country, but through decades of mobilization and strategic engagement with ruling elites, these advocates have adeptly identified and exposed the systemic gender discrimination embedded in the theocracy. They reject any insincere or cynical attempts at reform that merely offer an illusion of change while maintaining Iran's deeply rooted patriarchal authoritarianism.

For instance, in summer 2024, many women's rights advocates publicly campaigned for the boycott of the presidential elections, which they viewed as inherently undemocratic and illegitimate (Tajali 2024c). By abstaining from the electoral process, women challenge the regime's claims of legitimacy and electoral integrity, while also highlighting their demands for radical democratic change. Women's demands for radical change extends beyond merely increasing the number of women in decision-making roles, as many fear co-optation of women policy makers in inherently theocratic and undemocratic structures.

Women's ongoing resistance is also evident in their courageous acts of civil disobedience, particularly defying mandatory hijab laws by appearing unveiled in public despite state's threats. Women's defiance, which has emboldened as part of the recent women-led protests, has led to a growing number of men supporting women's fundamental demands for bodily autonomy, recognizing that these struggles are integral to broader ideals of democracy, freedom, and equality (Tajali 2024a).

A gendered analysis of state institutions not only reveals the extent of authoritarian backlash but also guides strategic feminist resistance against seemingly gender-neutral structures. This approach exposes the depth of

depth of authoritarian entrenchment and underscores the role of feminist resistance in safeguarding democratic values. ♦

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